

Printed Graphene/ WS₂ Battery-free Wireless Photosensor on Papers

Ting Leng^{a,1}, Khaled Parvez^{b,1}, Kewen Pan^a, Junaid Ali^b, Daryl McManus^b, Kostya S. Novoselov^{c,d}, Cinzia Casiraghi^{b,2*} and Zhirun Hu^{a,d,2*}

^aDepartment of Electrical and Electronic Engineering, University of Manchester, Manchester M13 9PL, U.K

^bDepartment of Chemistry, University of Manchester, Manchester M13 9PL, UK.

^cDepartment of Physics and Astronomy, University of Manchester, Manchester M13 9PL, UK.

^dNational Institute of Graphene, Manchester M13 9PL, UK.

¹T.Leng and K.Parvez contribute equally to this work.

²To whom the correspondence should be addressed E-mail: cinzia.casiraghi@manchester.ac.uk, z.hu@manchester.ac.uk

Received xxxxxx

Accepted for publication xxxxxx

Published xxxxxx

Abstract

Screen-printed graphene near field communication (NFC) tag antenna is integrated with inkjet-printed WS₂ photodetector on paper substrate to fabricate battery-free wireless photosensor. A sequential multi-stack printing is employed for the wireless photosensor fabrication: the NFC tag antenna is first screen-printed with graphene conductive ink and then the photodetector is inkjet-printed with transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs) WS₂ ink as photoactive component. High responsivity and sensitivity are observed for the WS₂ photodetector, which acts as photoactive thermistor of the NFC sensor IC chip. The highly conductive graphene nanoflakes ink enables the screen-printed graphene NFC tag antenna to withdraw sufficient power wirelessly from the reader to power the sensor IC chip. This work demonstrates a prospective approach to manufacture 2D materials enabled electronics where the electronic circuits (normally having a large size) can be realized by mass production screen printing and the sensing component (normally having a small size) can be produced by inkjet printing, enabling low cost and simple fabrication methods, compatible with flexible substrates such as paper.

Keywords: 2D materials, printed electronics, screen printing, inkjet printing, graphene, WS₂, photodetectors

1. Introduction

The discovery of novel nanomaterials with outstanding properties and the development of simple fabrications techniques have strongly increased the demands in low cost, widespread, integrated printed electronics applications[1,2]. The substrate is a decisive factor for the selection of the fabrication technologies and for the final application. In contrast to conventional substrates for printed electronics, such as glass and plastic, paper is one of the cheapest flexible substrates, which is also disposable and recyclable[3,4]. Thus, a large amount of research is currently dedicated to devices fabricated on paper[5–10].

Graphene, a single layer of graphite, is the most researched 2-dimensional (2D) material due to its outstanding properties[11]. It can be produced in solution by liquid phase exfoliation (LPE)[12]. LPE can be also used to exfoliate other 2D materials, including conducting materials such as graphene, semiconducting materials such as transition metal dicalcogenides (TMDs) and insulating materials such as hexagonal Boron Nitride (h-BN)[13]. The exfoliated graphene and other 2D materials can be processed for ink formulation for screen and inkjet printing, enabling the development of fully-printable 2D materials electronics[14,15]. Given that each 2D material has different properties, there is a very promising potential and prospect for the manufacturing of low-cost, large-scale printed functional devices[11–13,16–19].

2D material inks are proven to possess unique electronic, optical and mechanical properties, which have demonstrated excellent compatibility with paper substrates using traditional printing techniques, such as screen printing and inkjet printing [10,17,20–23]. Among 2D materials, graphene's high conductivity and strength make it an ideal material for the fabrication of low cost printed flexible interconnects, electrodes and antennas [8–10,16,17,20–23]. TMDs are layered compounds with an indirect band gap, which changes to direct gap upon exfoliating to single layer [24,25]. Integrated with graphene electrodes, the complementary electronic properties of TMDs can be used to fabricate photodetectors [26,27].

Most of the materials employed for printed electronics require rather harsh post-printing treatment like heating and acid treatments, which causes compatibility problems with many flexible substrates such as papers, textiles, plastic and elastomers[28]. Furthermore, the difficulties in recycling and the rapid accumulation of waste electronic devices in recent years have become insurmountable problems to the environment. The answer for both disposable and flexible electronics lies in using low-cost, biodegradable, and flexible substrates such as paper[3]. Furthermore, the porosity in paper allows fast absorption of the solvent, allowing the drop spacing to be minimized during printing for inkjet printing [21] and ink thick layer deposition in screen printing [10].

The combination of the two printing techniques, where screen-printing can fabricate large area electronic circuits and inkjet printing can fabricate sensing components, has the potential to achieve fully-printed 2D materials electronics on paper.

In this work we use inkjet and screen printing 2D material inks made in our groups[10,21,22] to develop an all-printed, battery-free, wireless enabled 2D materials based photosensor on paper substrate. The photodetector is made by printing a heterostructure consisting of graphene as the electrodes and WS₂ as the photosensitive material connected to the NFC sensor IC chip as a photoactive thermistor. The IC chip is then connected to screen printed graphene NFC tag antenna for wireless power harvesting and data transmission. The highly conductive graphene ink enables the printed graphene NFC tag antenna to withdraw sufficient power wirelessly from the reader to power the sensor IC chip and transmit the data back to the reader. The wireless battery-free photosensor demonstrates high responsivity and sensitivity.

2. Materials preparation and methods

2.1 Inkjet printed WS₂ photodetector

Graphite (100+ mesh), WS₂ tungsten (IV) disulfide powder, (<2 μm, 99% grade) and 1-pyrenesulfonic acid sodium (PS1) salt (purity > 97.0%) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich. Both the graphene and WS₂ inks were formulated from their bulk counterparts via ultrasonic assisted liquid-phase exfoliation. Briefly, 1.5g of WS₂ powder and 0.5g of PS1 was dispersed in 500 ml of deionized water and sonicated at 600 W using a Hilsonic bath sonicator for 5 days at constant temperature of 15 °C. Afterwards, the dispersion was centrifuged at 903g for 20 minutes using a Sigma 1-14k refrigerated centrifuge to collect the supernatant and to remove unexfoliated WS₂. The collected supernatant has a proper monolayer percentage and flake size suitable for inkjet printing. The supernatant was then centrifuged again at 16600 g for 60 minute to remove excess PS1. The collected precipitate was then re-dispersed in the inkjet printable water-based solvent, whose composition has been described in Ref[21]. The inkjet printable graphene ink was prepared using the same procedure described above. The concentration of inkjet printable graphene and WS₂ inks was carefully adjusted to 2 mg/mL. Photodetectors were printed with a Fujifilm Dimatix DMP-2800 piezoelectric inkjet printer through cartridges with a nozzle diameter of 21 μm. During the inkjet printing, neither the nozzles nor the substrate was heated. Samples with 40, 50, 60 passes of WS₂ were printed as photoactive layer, while the electrodes were printed with 20 passes of graphene ink. The devices were printed on technical paper (PEL P60) substrate (Printed Electronics Ltd). This substrate

ensures optimal printability as compared to standard (i.e. for office use) paper.

2.2 Screen printed graphene electrodes and NFC

Graphite flakes (Alfa Aesar, 325 mesh, purity: 99.8%) were dispersed in 400 mL of N-Methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP) (Sigma, anhydrous, purity: 99.5%) in a concentration of 20 mg/mL and shear mixed at 8000 rpm using Silverson L4R mixer equipped with square hole high shear screen for 2h at the constant temperature of 20 °C. The obtained dispersion then is transferred into glass bottle and bath ultra-sonicated (SHESTO, UT8061-EUK) for 24 hr. After that, the mixture is first filtered with 300-mesh stainless steel screen then the supernatant was carefully collected after centrifuged for 20 min at 500 rpm to remove any thick and unexfoliated flakes. The resulting dispersion is then vacuum filtered with Whatman filter paper grade 5 to remove the NMP. The graphene flakes collected on filter paper are re-dispersed in viscous solvent Ethylene Glycol (Alfa Aesar, anhydrous, purity: 99%) at concentration of 70 mg ml⁻¹ for screen printing. Screen printing was performed using semiautomatic screen printer with a 70° angle squeegee, at a printing speed of 50-150 mm s⁻¹. The printing screen with 24 mesh was fabricated and patterned with capillary film (ULANO, EZ50-Orange) to achieve the resolution and the adequate ink deposition for the printed circuit/electrodes. Normal printing papers (Xerox Colotech A4 Paper 250 gsm) were used as substrate.

3. Results and Discussions

There are two ways to connect a sensor to the RFID tag: the first method consists in printing the sensor directly on the RFID tag antenna, while the second method consists in connecting the two devices through an analogue-to-digital converter (ADC).

We started by investigating the first approach: a large size WS₂ photodetector was printed with active area of 1.5 mm x 1.5 mm, and was integrated with a screen-printed graphene meander line, Figure 1a. As the roughness of the screen printed graphene electrode may form pinholes in WS₂ layer and cause shorting, a thick WS₂ layer (thickness >500 nm) was printed. The thickness of the WS₂ layer cannot be measured accurately due to the roughness of the paper substrate. The top electrode was inkjet-printed to touch the second screen-printed graphene electrode, so that a bias could be applied via the screen printed structure. The meander line structure was used for better experimental observation and alignment test. Although the I-V measurements show relatively good photocurrent (Figure 1c), a slow response time was observed. Thus this approach was aborted, and the second approach was investigated and adopted, i.e. the printed photodetector was connected to the

chip on the printed graphene NFC tag antenna, which has the ability to read out values of the connected resistive component accurately from embedded ADC converter and transmit the data wirelessly through near field communication to the reader. The chip was powered wirelessly through drawing power from the magnetite field emitted by the NFC reader.

Figure 1. (a) Schematic and (b) Optical image of the inkjet printed WS₂ photodetector integrated with screen printed graphene meandered line. (c) I-V characteristics of the photodetector device shown in (b).

A parametric study on the NFC tag antenna geometries has been carried out numerically in order to design the antenna with best possible performance. The printed graphene NFC tag antennas were simulated with different geometrical parameters: number of turns N , width of the coil W and spacing between the adjacent coils S . The inductance L_{ant} and resistance R_{ant} can be obtained from the simulation. The quality factor of the antenna can be calculated from the resistance and inductance [29]. CST Microwave Studios was used for the NFC tag antenna simulation[30]. The printed graphene conductor was modelled as ohmic sheet with 1.5 Ω/sq. Simulated performance of the antennas with different structures is summarized for comparisons in Table 1. The size of the final NFC tag antenna is 74 mm × 53 mm, fits in the credit card size limitation under ID-1 of ISO/IEC 7810 standard. For screen printed graphene antennas, a wide conductor width helps to reduce the ohmic loss. Because of the limited tag size, the tag antenna with more turns of coil is unable to have a wide conductor width W , such as 4 turns and 5 turns tag antennas, causing high resistance which hinders the performance. For this reason it can be observed from simulation that even with higher inductance from the 4 turns and 5 turns tag antennas, the antenna that gives the best performance is 3 turns one with width $W = 5$ mm, spacing S

= 0.5 mm and quality factor of 0.752. This design pattern is used in the screen patterning for screen-printing. The fabricated screen printed NFC tag antenna prototype was then connected to a calibrated Vector Network Analyzer (VNA, Fieldfox N9918A, Keysight) using a SMA connector and characterized in polar mode to measure the tag antenna impedance. The resistance is obtained as 71.2 Ω and the inductance is 0.54 μH at 13.56MHz. The corresponding quality factor is calculated as 0.65, slightly lower than simulation of 0.752 but the NFC tag has been verified experimentally to still be able to function properly. This is caused by unflatness of the exposed screen resulting in variations in sheet resistance of the printed antenna. The WS_2 photodetector is connected to the specially designed tiny PCB which holds the conversion circuit and functional NFC chip (RF430FRL152H; Texas Instruments). The PCB is then connected to the screen printed NFC tag antenna using conductive epoxy (CW2400, Circuitworks).

Table 1. Simulation results for printed graphene NFC tag with different geometrical parameters.

No. of turns	Width W (mm)	Spacing S (mm)	Inductance L_{ant} (μH)	Resistance R_{ant} (Ω)	Quality factor
3	3	0.5	0.844	125.980	0.571
	3	1	0.791	121.780	0.553
	3	2	0.688	115.500	0.508
	4	0.5	0.710	89.640	0.674
	4	1	0.663	86.410	0.654
	4	2	0.579	81.610	0.605
	5	0.5	0.593	67.270	0.752
	5	1	0.551	65.020	0.722
	5	2	0.479	61.070	0.669
4	2	0.5	0.911	288.310	0.269
	2	1	0.913	269.940	0.288
	2	2	0.765	243.930	0.267
	3	0.5	0.772	191.680	0.343
	3	1	0.764	177.350	0.367
	3	2	0.651	156.530	0.354
	4	0.5	0.647	138.780	0.397
	4	1	0.620	124.260	0.425
	4	2	0.480	109.370	0.374
5	1	0.5	1.053	701.660	0.128
	1	1	0.960	659.680	0.124
	1	2	0.904	590.150	0.131
	2	0.5	1.456	352.140	0.352
	2	1	1.341	321.530	0.355
	2	2	1.072	278.540	0.328
	3	0.5	1.242	220.850	0.479
	3	1	1.066	199.990	0.454
	3	2	0.796	168.650	0.402

Figure 2. (a) Schematic of an all-printed heterostructure photodetector on a paper substrate, showing the graphene top (Gr_T) and bottom (Gr_B) electrodes and the WS_2 active layer in between. (b) Left: optical image of the device printed onto PEL P60 paper. Right: magnified optical image of the device corresponding to the red square in left image.

Figure 3. I-V curves of the photodetectors with increasing laser source ($\lambda = 532 \text{ nm}$) power density made with 40 (a), 50 (b) and 60 (c) print passes of WS_2 . (d) Photocurrent measured at $V_b = 2.5 \text{ V}$ as a function of increasing laser power density. The lines show the linear fit of the data, for each device.

We have printed WS_2 photodetectors with 40, 50 and 60 print passes. Figure 2a shows the structure of the heterostructured photodetector. Three photodetectors were printed on the same piece of paper under exactly the same conditions. Figure 2b shows an optical micrograph of one of the photodetector, where the interface between the different

layers can be clearly seen. The I-V characteristics, in dark and under illumination, of the WS₂ photodetector (active area 2.25 mm²) were taken using a laser source (532 nm) of 3 mm beam diameter. The laser power is calibrated with optical power meter ML910A. Keithley 4200-SCS Semiconductor Characterization System is connected to the graphene electrode, while sweeping the voltage and recording the current. The current flowing across the samples with a sweeping voltage from -2.5V to 2.5V under constant laser power densities of 0 mW/cm² (dark conditions), 44.1 mW/cm², 90.1 mW/cm², 128.0 mW/cm², 172.6 mW/cm² have been measured, respectively. As shown in Figure 3a - c, the I-V curves of all three photodetectors are symmetric with non-Ohmic behavior where the resistance is observed to decrease with increasing laser power densities. Figure 3d shows the photocurrent measured at bias voltage V_b = 2.5 V as a function of increasing laser power. The photoresponsivity of the printed photodetectors were 0.61, 0.46 and 0.41 mA/W for devices with 40, 50 and 60 print passes of WS₂, respectively.

Figure 4. Wireless measurement of WS₂ photodetector integrated with NFC. (a) Measurement setup; (b) Device prototype layout; (c) Wireless measurement when the laser source ($\lambda = 532$ nm) is on.

Figure 5. Wireless measurement results of WS₂ photodetector integrated with NFC. (a) 40 print passes; (b) 50 print passes; (c) 60 print passes.

The photoresponses (change of resistance) of the integrated wireless printed graphene/WS₂ photosensors for different WS₂ samples under different laser power densities have been measured wirelessly using the measurement setup in Figure 4 and the results are shown in Figure 5. The same laser source for I-V characteristic measurement in Figure 1 was used whilst the reading is wirelessly transmitted to NFC reader (TRF7970A, Texas Instruments) and read out by a PC. The measured results show that the samples made with 40, 50, 60 WS₂ printing passes all experience large resistance changes for different laser power densities.

The real time photoresponse of the wireless printed graphene/WS₂ photosensor for a pulsed incident laser signal has also been measured for the sample made with 40 and 60 printing passes, as shown in Figure 6. Each on/off state of the laser was set for approximately 60s, laser power density is 172.6 mW/cm² for the on state. It can be seen that good repeatability is achieved for both samples during total measurement time of 300s. The resistance increases as the thickness of the semiconducting layer (which dominates the total resistance) increases. The large change in resistance in on/off conditions indicates good responses to laser illumination, confirming instantaneous photodetection and successful wireless data transmission.

Figure 6. Wireless responsivity measurement of WS₂ photodetector integrated NFC. (a) 40 print passes; (b) 60 print passes.

4. Conclusions

In this work, we have developed printed graphene/WS₂ enabled functional RF electronic device by combining large scale industrial screen-printing technology for large size and high conductive antennas and high resolution inkjet printing for more dedicated and smaller size heterostructured sensing devices. In addition, both antennas and sensing devices were printed on paper substrate, which is relatively low cost, biodegradable and disposable. Inkjet printed WS₂ photodetector was successfully integrated with screen printed graphene NFC tag antennas for wireless light sensing applications were demonstrated experimentally, revealing the potential of combining different printing technologies for development of printed 2D material-based devices for wireless sensing and IoT applications, compatible with low cost and flexible paper substrate. Inkjet printed sensing electronic components, along with reliable, inexpensive and large-scale screen printed circuit have a promising future in taking paper printed electronics to the next level without worrying compromising performance or substantially increasing the production cost for RF electronics.

Acknowledgements

This work has been supported by the Grand Challenge EPSRC grant EP/N010345/1 and the RFID SHP2 project in the framework of the graphene flagship (grant agreement No 785219). CC also acknowledges support by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the ICT project WASP (grant agreement No. 825213).

References

- [1] Chang J S, Facchetti A F and Reuss R 2017 A Circuits and Systems Perspective of Organic/Printed Electronics: Review, Challenges, and Contemporary and Emerging Design Approaches *IEEE J. Emerg. Sel. Top. Circuits Syst.* **7** 7–26
- [2] Mohammed M G and Kramer R 2017 All-Printed Flexible and Stretchable Electronics *Adv. Mater.* **29** 1604965
- [3] Tobjörk D and Österbacka R 2011 Paper Electronics *Adv. Mater.* **23** 1935–61
- [4] Cruz S M F, Rocha L A and Viana J C 2018 Printing Technologies on Flexible Substrates for Printed Electronics *Flexible Electronics (InTech)*
- [5] Ha D, Fang Z and Zhitenev N B 2018 Paper in Electronic and Optoelectronic Devices *Adv. Electron. Mater.* **4** 1700593
- [6] Zhang Y, Zhang L, Cui K, Ge S, Cheng X, Yan M, Yu J and Liu H 2018 Flexible Electronics Based on Micro/Nanostructured Paper *Adv. Mater.* **30** 1801588
- [7] Huang X, Leng T, Zhang X, Chen J C, Chang K H, Geim A K, Novoselov K S and Hu Z 2015 Binder-free highly conductive graphene laminate for low cost printed radio frequency applications *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **106** 203105
- [8] Huang X, Leng T, Zhu M, Zhang X, Chen J, Chang K, Aqeeli M, Geim A K, Novoselov K S and Hu Z 2016 Highly Flexible and Conductive Printed Graphene for Wireless Wearable Communications Applications *Sci. Rep.* **5** 18298
- [9] Huang X, Leng T, Chang K H, Chen J C, Novoselov K S and Hu Z 2016 Graphene radio frequency and microwave passive components for low cost wearable electronics *2D Mater.* **3** 025021
- [10] Pan K, Fan Y, Leng T, Li J, Xin Z, Zhang J, Hao L, Gallop J, Novoselov K S and Hu Z 2018 Sustainable production of highly conductive multilayer graphene ink for wireless connectivity and IoT applications *Nat. Commun.* **9** 5197
- [11] Novoselov K S, Fal'ko V I, Colombo L, Gellert P R, Schwab M G and Kim K 2012 A roadmap for graphene *Nature* **490** 192–200
- [12] Hernandez Y, Nicolosi V, Lotya M, Blighe F M, Sun Z, De S, McGovern I T, Holland B, Byrne M, Gun'ko Y K, Boland J J, Niraj P, Duesberg G, Krishnamurthy S, Goodhue R, Hutchison J, Scardaci V, Ferrari A C and Coleman J N 2008 High-yield production of graphene by liquid-phase exfoliation of graphite. *Nat. Nanotechnol.* **3** 563–8
- [13] Coleman J N, Lotya M, O'Neill A, Bergin S D, King P J, Khan U, Young K, Gaucher A, De S, Smith R J, Shvets I V., Arora S K, Stanton G, Kim H Y, Lee K, Kim G T, Duesberg G S, Hallam T, Boland J J, Wang J J, Donegan J F, Grunlan J C, Moriarty G, Shmeliov A, Nicholls R J, Perkins J M, Grievson E M, Theuwissen K, McComb D W, Nellist P D and Nicolosi V 2011 Two-dimensional nanosheets produced by liquid exfoliation of layered materials *Science (80-.)*. **331** 568–71
- [14] Hu G, Albrow-Owen T, Jin X, Ali A, Hu Y, Howe R C T, Shehzad K, Yang Z, Zhu X, Woodward R I, Wu T C, Jussila H, Wu J Bin, Peng P, Tan P H, Sun Z, Kelleher E J R, Zhang M, Xu Y and Hasan T 2017 Black phosphorus ink formulation for inkjet printing of optoelectronics and photonics *Nat. Commun.* **8**
- [15] Hu G, Kang J, Ng L W T, Zhu X, Howe R C T,

- 1
2
3 Jones C G, Hersam M C and Hasan T 2018
4 Functional inks and printing of two-dimensional
5 materials *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **47** 3265–300
- 6 [16] Leng T, Huang X, Chang K, Chen J, Abdalla M A
7 and Hu Z 2016 Graphene Nanoflakes Printed
8 Flexible Meandered-Line Dipole Antenna on Paper
9 Substrate for Low-Cost RFID and Sensing
10 Applications *IEEE Antennas Wirel. Propag. Lett.* **15**
11 1565–8
- 12 [17] Worsley R, Pimpolari L, McManus D, Ge N,
13 Ionescu R, Wittkopf J A, Alieva A, Basso G,
14 Macucci M, Iannaccone G, Novoselov K S, Holder
15 H, Fiori G and Casiraghi C 2019 All-2D Material
16 Inkjet-Printed Capacitors: Toward Fully Printed
17 Integrated Circuits *ACS Nano* **13** 54–60
- 18 [18] Divitini G, Ren J, Cacovich S, Torrisi F, Ducati C,
19 Mansouri A, Sordan R, Kim J M, Wang C and Carey
20 T 2017 Fully inkjet-printed two-dimensional material
21 field-effect heterojunctions for wearable and textile
22 electronics *Nat. Commun.* **8**
- 23 [19] Kelly A G, Hallam T, Backes C, Harvey A,
24 Esmacily A S, Godwin I, Coelho J, Nicolosi V,
25 Lauth J, Kulkarni A, Kinge S, Siebbeles L D A,
26 Duesberg G S and Coleman J N 2017 All-printed
27 thin-film transistors from networks of liquid-
28 exfoliated nanosheets *Science (80-.)*. **356** 69–73
- 29 [20] McManus D, Dal Santo A, Selvasundaram P B,
30 Krupke R, LiBassi A and Casiraghi C 2018
31 Photocurrent study of all-printed photodetectors on
32 paper made of different transition metal
33 dichalcogenide nanosheets *Flex. Print. Electron.* **3**
34 034005
- 35 [21] McManus D, Vranic S, Withers F, Sanchez-
36 Romaguera V, Macucci M, Yang H, Sorrentino R,
37 Parvez K, Son S-K, Iannaccone G, Kostarelos K,
38 Fiori G and Casiraghi C 2017 Water-based and
39 biocompatible 2D crystal inks for all-inkjet-printed
40 heterostructures *Nat. Nanotechnol.* **12** 343–50
- 41 [22] Huang X, Leng T, Georgiou T, Abraham J,
42 Raveendran Nair R, Novoselov K S and Hu Z 2018
43 Graphene Oxide Dielectric Permittivity at GHz and
44 Its Applications for Wireless Humidity Sensing *Sci.*
45 *Rep.* **8** 43
- 46 [23] Alburaihan A, Aqeeli M, Chen J C, Leng T, Hu Z,
47 Chang K H and Huang X 2015 Electromagnetic
48 interference shielding based on highly flexible and
49 conductive graphene laminate *Electron. Lett.* **51**
50 1350–2
- 51 [24] Klekachev A V., Nourbakhsh A, Asselberghs I,
52 Stesmans A L, Heyns M M and De Gendt S 2013
53 Graphene Transistors and Photodetectors *Interface*
54 *Mag.* **22** 63–8
- 55 [25] Splendiani A, Sun L, Zhang Y, Li T, Kim J, Chim
56 C-Y, Galli G and Wang F 2010 Emerging
57 Photoluminescence in Monolayer MoS₂ *Nano Lett.*
58 **10** 1271–5
- 59 [26] Withers F, Yang H, Britnell L, Rooney A P, Lewis
60 E, Felten A, Woods C R, Sanchez Romaguera V,
Georgiou T, Eckmann A, Kim Y J, Yeates S G,
Haigh S J, Geim A K, Novoselov K S and Casiraghi
C 2014 Heterostructures produced from nanosheet-
based inks *Nano Lett.* **14** 3987–92
- [27] Britnell L, Ribeiro R M, Eckmann A, Jalil R, Belle
B D, Mishchenko A, Kim Y J, Gorbachev R V.,
Georgiou T, Morozov S V., Grigorenko A N, Geim
A K, Casiraghi C, Castro Neto A H and Novoselov K
S 2013 Strong light-matter interactions in
heterostructures of atomically thin films *Science (80-
.)*. **340** 1311–4
- [28] Li X, Mahdi Honari M, Fu Y, Kumar A, Saghlatoon
H, Mousavi P and Chung H-J 2017 Self-reinforcing
graphene coatings on 3D printed elastomers for
flexible radio frequency antennas and strain sensors
Flex. Print. Electron. **2** 035001
- [29] Semiconductors N X P 2014 AN11535
Measurement and tuning of a NFC and Reader IC
antenna with a MiniVNA 1–29
- [30] Dassault Systèmes 2019 CST Microwave Studios
2017